

Mathematical Creativity and Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Oruk Anam Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study investigated "Mathematical Creativity and Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Oruk Anam Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State". Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A correlational survey design was adopted. The sample size for the study was 120 students through a purposive sampling technique. The Mathematical Creativity Questionnaire (MCQ) was the validated instrument used for data collection with a reliability coefficient of 0.97. Analysis of data for the study was done using the correlation and regression statistical tool to answer research questions as well as testing of the hypotheses. Findings from the study revealed that mathematical creativity has a significant relationship with the academic performance of students and enhances creative thinking among secondary school students. Based on the findings, it is recommended, among others, that the government ensure that science teachers undergo standard training and creativity tests to make them skilled and qualified teachers in order to meet its educational objectives; stakeholders in education should motivate mathematical teachers to teach the subject effectively to arouse creativity and scientific consciousness in the students. Secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State should be provided with necessary learning aids such as standard slides, well-equipped libraries, a mathematical creativity aptitude box, among others, to enhance teachers' and students' involvement in learning. This will help foster students' mathematical creativity in mathematics.

Keywords: Mathematics, Creativity, Mathematics Creativity, Problem-Solving and Academic Performance

Background of the Study

In recognition of its roles as major machinery behind any nation's advancement in science and technology and its immense contributions towards individual capacity building, mathematics has unavoidably registered itself in the school curriculum right from the primary up to the tertiary level of the education system in Nigeria. No wonder mathematics is a major requirement for securing admission into higher institutions of learning as well as a "scale" used in testing people's level of intelligence before offering them jobs in the country (Adeniji, 2019).

Mathematics is a compulsory subject at the secondary school level because of its utility in society. The subject matter of mathematics cuts across every discipline to a varied degree. Onwudire (2015) posited that everybody, as well as every nation, needs the presence of mathematics for development. Given that mathematics is very important for personal, organisational and societal development, it has been globally observed that the content of general or ordinary mathematics is not sufficient for some higher courses in the tertiary institution; hence, the emergence of further mathematics as a school subject. The Nigerian society keyed into this global trend and advocated that further mathematics should be included as one of the senior secondary school subjects. Participation of students in further mathematics is expected to increase undergraduate students' participation in courses such as the sciences, engineering, mathematics and technology (Lyakhova and Neate, 2018).

Mathematics is a science that deals with the logic of space, quantity and arrangement (Kosmas 2004). It takes a central position in science and technology. The objectives of the mathematics curriculum at the senior secondary school level include knowing and demonstrating understanding of the concepts from the five branches of mathematics (number, algebra, geometry, trigonometry and discrete mathematics). Therefore, mathematics is to develop both the individual and the entire society. It is a necessary prerequisite and integral part of such professions as chartered accountant, data analyst, data scientist, investment analyst, and research scientist, to mention but a few.

Mathematics is the precursor of science and technology and an indispensable single element in modern societal development. This suggests that there could be no real development technologically without a corresponding development in mathematics, both as conceived and practised. As it is rightly observed in Kyari (2018), no nation can make any meaningful progress in this information technology age, particularly in economic development, whose foundation is science and mathematics. Mathematics is the science of measurement, quantity and magnitude. It is also referred to as the abstract science which

investigates deductively the conclusions implicit in the elementary conceptions of spatial and numerical relations. It is also defined as the science of number and space. Mathematics is also called the science of logical reasoning. Locke had said, "Mathematics is a way to settle in the mind a habit of reasoning." Here the results are developed through a process of reasoning. The reasoning in mathematics is of a peculiar kind and possesses a number of characteristics such as simplicity, accuracy, certainty of result, originality and verification.

Mathematical problem-solving is considered one of the many endpoints in teaching mathematics to students. This study looked into the performance in mathematics problem-solving among fourth-year students of Central Mindanao University Laboratory High School and their relationship with students' attitudes towards mathematics. The attitudes measured were attitude towards success in mathematics, mother's mathematics attitude, father's mathematics attitude, motivation, usefulness of mathematics, teacher's mathematics attitude, confidence in learning mathematics, and mathematics anxiety (Dennis, 2018).

Mathematics education is required to meet up with the increase in demand for science and technology by private and government establishments. Without effective mathematics education, the nation will likely become impoverished. This is because the natural resources which abound in Nigeria need to be harnessed, processed and converted to needed products for optimum use (Aduwa 2010). Mathematics education in Nigeria has received attention over the last 50 years. During this period a lot of reforms have taken place in the mathematics education curriculum. To make a breakthrough in science and technology education, this will depend quite well on the level of our mathematics development and achievement in the country. Issues to address in achieving this breakthrough include weakness in current mathematics teachers, curriculum reforms, mathematics teachers' availability and competence, gender and stigmatisation in mathematics, learner interest, funding and performance assessment and evaluation. With mathematics education as the springboard for any meaningful development in science and technology, any reforms taking place in education must focus on the mathematics education unit with lots of concern to address most of the bottlenecks in this presentation. Steven, Akwana & Maaji (2018).

However, as important as mathematics is, science educators have been lamenting over the poor performance and interest of students in the subject in the secondary schools for the past decades (Nzekwe 2018). Students' poor performance and interest in mathematics for quite a long time now have resulted in an inadequate number of students

offering mathematics-orientated courses in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The persistent poor performance has also contributed to a poor economy, poor industrialisation, lack of jobs and starvation, to mention but a few. Professionals required to take care of those problems can only be effectively produced through mathematics education. Many factors have been attributed to the observed poor performance and lack of interest in mathematics by students. This has called for a boost in mathematical creativity and thereby improves students' academic performance in secondary schools.

Creativity is traditionally supposed to be attributed to art and literature, but nowadays doing meaningful science has also been considered a creative act. In areas of art and literature, it is generally enough to create an extraordinary and novel work, but a creative scientific idea needs not only to be novel but also useful (Neumann, 2007). Technological advances in today's society have been owed to the creativity of scientists and mathematicians. The critical role of these creative mathematicians, who have been able to create new mathematical insights and ideas, is so apparent that there is no need to be emphasised. However, the study of processes of their creative thinking is valuable. Creativity involves "the openness to ideas and the willingness to encourage the exploration of the unknown, even if not easily manageable".

Creativity in education has been viewed since the late 1990s as globally relevant in ways never seen before Craft (2005). Once thought of only as an artistic quality, creativity has become sought after by engineers, executives, and researchers. Anastasia and Anwar, cited in Anwar, Aness, Khizar, Naseer and Muhammad (2012), quoted Albert Einstein as saying, "We can't solve problems by using the same kind of thinking we used when we created them." Creative thinking has been categorised as something we are born with, but others have said that it can be developed through activities and teaching strategies. Creative thinking is a way of generating ideas that can in some way be applied to the world. This often involves problem-solving utilising particular aspects of intelligence, for example, linguistic, mathematical and interpersonal (Anwar et al., 2012).

Creative thinking involves creating something new or original. It involves the skills of flexibility, originality, fluency, imagery, associative thinking, attribute listing, metaphorical thinking and forced relationships. The aim of creative thinking is to stimulate curiosity and promote divergence. Gough (1991), cited in Anwar et al. (2012), said, "Perhaps most importantly in today's information age, thinking skills are viewed as crucial for educated persons to cope with a rapidly changing world. Many educators believe that specific knowledge will not be as important to tomorrow's workers and citizens as the ability to learn and make sense of new information." Creative thinking is a novel way of

seeing and doing things that is characterised by four components: fluency (generating ideas), flexibility (shifting perspectives easily), originality (consisting of something new), and elaboration (building on existing ideas).

Mathematical creativity is often considered the exclusive domain of professional mathematicians (Sriraman, 2005). The French mathematician Henri Poincaré believed that discovery in mathematics is a combination of ideas and stated that there are a lot of these combinations, but a few of them are useful. In the process of finding these useful combinations, a great number of combinations are constructed, and then meaningful combinations are distinguished from meaningless ones. In other words, creating could be defined as forming, recognising and choosing important and useful combinations. Also, Boden (2004) states that combining familiar ideas in unfamiliar manners can also be considered a creative work.

Rather similar to these, Eryvnyck asserts that creating useful mathematical concepts through combining previously known concepts or discovering unknown relations between mathematical facts can be considered as a creative act of doing mathematics. Also, he emphasises that creativity in mathematics plays a key role in the full cycle of advanced mathematical thinking, which helps plausible conjectures to be made in order to develop mathematical theories and generates new mathematical knowledge. Chamberlin and Moon (2005) consider divergent thinking as one of the prevalent descriptors of mathematical creativity. Laycock described mathematical creativity as an ability to analyse a given problem from different perspectives, see patterns, differences and similarities, generate multiple ideas and choose a proper method to deal with unfamiliar mathematical situations (Idris & Nor, 2010).

At the school levels, mathematical creativity is seen as the process that results in unusual (novel) and/or insightful solution(s) to a given problem or analogous problems and/or the formulation of new questions and/or possibilities that allow an old problem to be regarded from a new angle. According to Sriraman's definition, at the school levels, some researchers believe that creativity in mathematics is generally associated with problem-solving or problem-posing (e.g., Chamberlin & Moon, 2005).

Colom and Lino in Chinelo (2020) saw gender as the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between masculinity and femininity populations. The importance of examining achievement in relation to gender is primarily based on the socio-cultural differences between girls and boys. Some trades such as the weaker sex; as such, they are expected to handle the relatively easy and less demanding tasks while the complex tasks are allocated to boys.

Also, certain science subjects, such as physics and mathematics, are regarded as male enterprises, while females tilt to areas like biology. It is noted that the issue of gender is an important one in science education, with increasing emphasis on ways of boosting manpower for technological development as well as increasing the population of females in science and technology fields. Gender has been identified as one of the factors influencing students' achievement in the sciences at the senior secondary school level (Ekenem 2011).

Problem-solving is the process of analysing a problem and resolving it in the best way possible for that situation. This process contains analysing the problem (root cause analysis), defining countermeasures for the problem and implementing the right solution for that situation. For problem-solving, people need critical thinking and analytical skills. Everybody within an organisation or company can benefit from having good skills because there are always problems. There have been lots of scientific and practical studies from a learning point of view. Some of the techniques developed and used in artificial intelligence (AI), computer science, engineering, mathematics, or medicine are related to mental techniques studied in psychology (Kousar, 2022).

Gender is a psychological term and a cultural constant developed by society to differentiate between the roles, behaviour, mental and emotional attributes of males and females (Chinelo, 2019). Iwendi (2009) reported that male students performed better than their female counterparts in science and mathematics concepts. The non-significant gender-related difference in performance could be attributed to the fact that both participated actively in the learning process, thus helping them to acquire meaningful learning. Hypothesis. For instance, Eccles and Wang (2015) emphasised that females express less interest in mathematics than their male peers. Gender is an analytic concept that describes sociological roles, cultural responsibilities and expectations of men and women in a given society or cultural setting (Chinelo, 2019). It describes the personality traits, attributes, behaviour, values, relative power, influence, roles and expectations (femininity and masculinity) that society ascribes to the two sexes on a differential basis (Ezeh, 2013).

The work, therefore, intended to investigate the effect of mathematics creativity and students' academic performance and interest in mathematics in secondary schools. The study therefore intended to ascertain the effectiveness of mathematical creativity on students' academic performance among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, when taught mathematics using creative learning and teaching strategies.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, mathematics is a compulsory subject up to the secondary school level. During the last couple of years, students' performance in mathematics had fallen below average. For instance, in 2023 the WAEC private candidates' results report showed that 44.95% passed Mathematics between A1 and C6. Recent findings indicate that the level of mathematics academic performance has remained persistently low. The National Examination Council (NECO) reports have continued to raise concern over the poor performance in secondary schools.

The student's poor academic performance and interest in mathematics are alarming in spite of the fact that much research has been carried out to ameliorate the poor situation. Many instructional approaches have been proffered by psychologists like Brunner, Piaget, and Gagné for improved performance and interest in mathematics and other science subjects. They strongly believed that the instructional approach adopted by mathematics teachers in teaching mathematics is to a large extent responsible for the observed consistent poor performance and interest in mathematics.

This study therefore intends to ascertain the effectiveness of mathematics creativity on students' academic performance in mathematics among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, when taught mathematics using creative learning and teaching strategies.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in mathematics among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area. Specifically, the study seeks to

- i. Examine the relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area.
- ii. Examine the relationship between gender, mathematical creativity and students' academic performance among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area.

Research Questions: The following questions were formulated for the study.

- i. What is the relationship between mathematical creativity and academic performance among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area?

- ii. What is the relationship between gender, mathematical creativity and academic performance among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area?

Research Hypotheses: The current study investigated the effects of mathematical creativity and students' academic performance among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study was guided by the following hypothesis:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between gender, mathematics creativity and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Significance of the Study

For students, it will provide peer groups with suggestions and feedback about what they should think and how they should solve mathematics problems in diverse ways other than the known traditional methods. Parents, it will enable parents to play a large role in how students function in everyday activities. Teachers, it is vital for education-related professionals to understand the need for mathematical creativity in order to influence negative attitudes towards the academic performance of students in mathematics. Teachers can grow and develop to acquire new knowledge, skills and attitudes which, in turn, promote or improve their teaching performance at different stages of their careers and tackle the students' negative traits within and outside the mathematics classroom. State Secondary Education Board (SSEB)/Ministry of Education; it will help the Ministry of Education to plan for the improvement in the educational sector in implementing the Education Development Blueprint. It means that the good integration between the government's efforts and teachers' commitment will lead to the achievement of the educational goal. School administrators, this study also will give advantages to all schools, especially administrators, where they can have a clear view on the education development blueprint and what the best approach is to be practised in order to achieve the desired goals. Finally, this study will enable the researcher to focus on the topic for further research.

Delimitations of the Study

There are many features of mathematical creativity, but this research is delimited to the investigation of the relationship between originality, flexibility, creative thinking and fluency in mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. This study is carried out in five public secondary schools in Oruk Anam Local Government Area to explore the relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary schools. This research investigated the perception of the causes of poor performance in mathematics and students' creativity in solving mathematical problems.

Limitations of the study: This study is limited by financial constraints, urban migration, poor mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary schools. This research investigated the perception of the causes of poor performance in mathematics and students' creativity in solving mathematical problems.

Definition of terms

Mathematics: Mathematics is the science of structure, order, logical reasoning and quantitative calculation and relation that has evolved from elemental practices of counting, measuring and describing the shapes of objects.

Creativity: Creativity is the ability to transcend traditional ways of thinking or acting and to develop new and original ideas, methods or objects. Creativity is a pattern of thinking and the capacity to accept challenges. Creativity is an ability that allows people to develop new ideas, but that still feels a bit vague and intangible. It is a skill that allows you to draw understanding of the world around you, connect those observations to your existing knowledge reservoirs, and imagine new applications of your knowledge in the world.

Mathematical Creativity: Mathematical creativity is an ability to analyse a given problem from different perspectives, see patterns, differences and similarities, generate multiple ideas and choose a proper method to deal with unfamiliar mathematical situations (Idris & Nor, 2010).

Problem Solving: Problem solving is the act of defining a problem, determining the cause of the problem, identifying, prioritising, and selecting alternatives for a solution, and implementing a solution.

Academic performance: This refers to cognitive ability as measured by tests, assignments and examinations which are used to determine their success or failure in school.

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational survey research design to examine the relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in mathematics. The design was considered appropriate because the researcher employed both quantitative questionnaire data and students' mathematics performance records from the previous academic session in gathering the required information. The population of the study consisted of all the fourteen public secondary schools with a total population of 17,890 students in the study area, according to records obtained from the State Secondary Education Board in 2013. A sample of students was selected from four public secondary schools using purposive random sampling techniques to ensure that the selected participants were relevant to the objectives of the study.

The instruments used for data collection were the Mathematical Creativity Questionnaire (MCQ) and students' previous academic performance results in mathematics examinations. The questionnaire was designed to measure the various dimensions of mathematical creativity, including originality, flexibility, fluency, divergent thinking, and elaboration. To ensure the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was submitted to the researcher's supervisor in the Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, University of Uyo, for expert scrutiny and validation. All corrections and suggestions provided were incorporated before the final administration of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.97, indicating that the instrument was highly reliable for the study. The questionnaire consisted of multiple-choice items with four response options: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), which were scored 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively.

The researcher personally visited the selected schools after obtaining permission from the principals and was introduced to the mathematics teachers for assistance during the data collection process. The Mathematical Creativity Questionnaire (MCQ) was administered to the students under the supervision of some teachers, while all completed copies of the instrument were retrieved immediately to avoid loss of data. In addition, students' academic performance records from previous mathematics examinations were collected to assess their level of mathematical creativity and achievement. The data obtained from the study were analysed using correlation and multiple regression statistical

techniques at the 0.05 level of significance to determine the relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in mathematics.

Results and Discussion

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between Mathematical Creativity and Academic performance among Secondary Schools Students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area?

Table 1: Correlation: Relationship between Students' Mathematics Creativity and Academic Performance

		AC SCORES	CREATIVITY
AC_SCORES	Pearson Correlation	1	.456**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	40	40
CREATIVIT Y	Pearson Correlation	.456**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	40	40

From Table 1 above, it shows that mathematical creativity has a positive correlation of 0.456 with students' academic achievement. Thus, it is empirically established that mathematical creativity apparently has a positive relationship with students' academic performance. This answered the research question that mathematical creativity has a positive relationship with the academic performance of students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between Mathematical Creativity and Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Table 2: Analysis of Scores of Mathematical Creativity.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r	r-cal	r-crit	Decision
Mathematical Creativity	40	2.79	0.36				
Academic Performance	40	51.35	12.82	0.45	7.93	0.3044	Rejected

Table 2 above explains that mathematical creativity has an r-cal of 7.93, which is greater than the r-critical of 0.3044. Hence, it is empirically established that students' mathematical creativity has a positive relationship with academic performance. From the above, the calculated r-cal of 7.93 is greater than the r-value critical of 0.3044 at alpha = 0.05 and df = 38. This means that there is a significant relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary schools. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected because there is a positive significant relationship between mathematical creativity and academic performance of students in mathematics in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between Gender and Mathematical Creativity on Students' Academic performance in Secondary Schools Students mathematics in Oruk Anam Local Government Area?

Table 3: Model Summary: Gender and Mathematical Creativity on Students' Academic Performance

Mode	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.467 ^a	.218	.175	11.64494

a. Predictors: (Constant), GENDER, CREATIVITY

From table 3 above, it shows gender and mathematical creativity are predictors of students' academic performance. This shows that gender and mathematical creativity have a positive correlation of 0.467 with students' academic achievement. With this, it is empirically established that gender and mathematical creativity jointly accounted for 21.8% of the variation in students' academic performance. This answered the research question: Do gender and mathematical creativity have a positive relationship with students' academic performance among secondary school mathematics students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area?

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between Gender and Mathematical Creativity on Students' Academic performance in Secondary Schools Mathematics in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

ANOVA^a: Gender and Mathematical Creativity on Academic Performance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1395.733	2	697.866	5.146	.011 ^b
	Residual	5017.367	37	135.605		
	Total	6413.100	39			

a. Dependent Variable: AC_SCORES

b. Predictors: (Constant), GENDER, CREATIVITY

Table 4 above shows that gender and mathematical creativity predict students' academic performance. This follows that the calculated F-value of 5.15 has a significant relationship of 0.011 at $p < 0.05$. This implies that there is a significant relationship between gender and mathematical creativity in students' academic performance in secondary schools. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that gender and mathematical creativity predict students' academic performance in secondary schools' mathematics.

Discussion of Results

This study examines the relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary school mathematics students and the relationship between gender and mathematical creativity on students' academic performance in secondary school mathematics students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The findings made in this study are discussed below.

There is a significant relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary schools in a mathematical creativity test conducted on secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. This implies that there is a significant relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary schools. This is in line with the view of Onwudire (2015), Ebenezer (2019), Adeyemo (2010), and Bhatt (2014), who reported that mathematical creativity has a significant relationship with the academic performance of students and it enhances creative thinking among secondary school students.

There is a significant relationship between gender, mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary schools. This implies that male students have higher mathematical creativity than the female students at the same mathematical creativity test; that is, they perform better and faster than their female counterparts.

Hence, it is concluded that gender and mathematical creativity are predictors of secondary school mathematics students' academic performance. This view was also shared by Ebenezer (2019), Kousar (2010) and Hyde (2008), who reported that gender and mathematical creativity have a significant relationship with the academic performance of students and that it enhances creative thinking among secondary school students.

Summary of Findings

The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between mathematics creativity and students' academic performance in secondary school mathematics students and the relationship between gender and mathematical creativity on students' academic performance in mathematics among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this aim, students were given freedom of choice to express their creative ability using a questionnaire which covers all the components of mathematics creativity.

The students' academic performance was compared using different statistical measures. It was discovered that students with mathematical creativity achieved significantly better and faster in problem-solving and creative thinking. This could be attributed to the mathematics creativity adopted by the teacher and students in the classroom. At first, students found divergent thinking and originality boring and time-consuming but later imbibed them in solving critical problems and also boosted their thinking ability even in everyday life. The null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The hypotheses were later rejected since it was found out that there is a significant relationship between mathematics creativity and students' academic performance of mathematics students, which were the variables considered. These findings agree with those of Oribhabor (2020), Ebenezer (2019), Kousar (2010) and Hyde (2008), who reported that mathematics creativity has a significant relationship with the academic performance of students and it enhances creative thinking among secondary school students. Also, it is reported that gender and mathematical creativity have a significant relationship with the academic performance of students, and it enhances creative thinking among secondary school students.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary: This study examines the relationship between mathematical creativity and students' academic performance in secondary school mathematics students and the relationship between gender and mathematical creativity on students' academic

performance in mathematics among secondary school students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The sample comprised 120 mathematics students, forming about 7% of the research population, randomly drawn from 4 secondary schools in Oruk Anam Local Government Area. A 20-item multi-scale instrument (Mathematical Creativity Questionnaire) was drawn, with a reliability of 0.97, which was used to collect relevant data, which were analysed using correlation and regression statistical analysis at the 0.05 level of significance. The results obtained were presented and discussed in chapter four. From the findings, it was discovered that mathematical creativity has a significant relationship with the academic performance of students, and it enhances creative thinking among secondary school students. Hence, teachers should help the students think outside the box by asking the critical questions and incorporate suitable activities into their lessons.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is here concluded that mathematical creativity has a significant relationship with the academic performance of students, and it enhances creative thinking among secondary school students. This should be adopted by teachers who are expected to bring out the creative ability from the students by helping them think creatively, thus building a nation of creative thinkers and problem solvers among secondary school students.

Implications of the Findings

- i. Developing problem-solving ability necessitates effective teaching and learning of mathematics and scientific concepts.
- ii. Students with mathematical creativity perform better and faster in any learned concepts and everyday life situations.
- iii. Mathematical creativity is most effective in terms of brainstorming, role-playing, questioning, think-pair-share, self-reflection, learning games and visual simulations but appears to be more advanced and time-consuming at first to the students and thereafter ensures creative problem solvers.

Recommendations: Based on the findings and conclusions reached in this study, the following recommendations are made.

- i. Teaching and learning of mathematical concepts and science in general should be brainstorming, role-playing, and question-filling in such a way that students can learn effectively and retain the concepts presented to them. Mathematical creativity seems

- to be relevant in achieving this goal, mostly in mathematics problem-solving classrooms. It should therefore be incorporated into the teaching of mathematics at the secondary school level.
- ii. In-service training programmes for mathematics teachers in the form of seminars, workshops and conferences should be conducted on the use and effectiveness of mathematical creativity, critical question technique and problem-solving strategy in the teaching of mathematics.
 - iii. Mathematics teachers should incorporate adequate activities, learning games and reflective thinking into their lessons for effective delivery.
 - iv. Adequate learning facilities should be made available by the government for effective teaching and learning of mathematics and any other science subjects.

Suggestions for Further Studies

- i. It is suggested that this study should be repeated with another population in a different study area.
- ii. A similar study should be carried out focusing on the teaching of a different subject and/or mathematical concept, using all the components of creativity.
- iii. A similar study should be conducted to investigate the effects of mathematical creativity and problem-solving methods on students' academic performance.

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MATHEMATICAL CREATIVITY QUESTIONNAIRE (MCQ)

Section A: Respondent’s Personal Data

Name _____ **of**

School:.....

Gender: Male () Female () **Age:** 13 – 14yrs () 15 – 16yrs () 17yrs and above ()

Section B:

Instruction: Please complete this section by ticking (√) against any of the columns that best represent your feeling. Each item has four response options; SA=Strongly Agree, A = Agree, D= Disagree, SD= Strongly Disagree.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD
1	I use different strategies to solve Mathematics problems.				
2	I develop new methods in solving Mathematics problems.				
3	I attempt challenging Mathematics problems.				
4	I believe that creativity comes by hard work and persistence				
5	I create Mathematics problems and solve them.				
6	I solve similar Mathematics problems quickly.				
7.	I create Mathematical model to solve real life problems				
8.	I stick to Mathematics problems until I have the solution.				
9.	I enjoy playing Mathematics puzzles.				
10.	I use diagrams to solve words problem.				
11.	I have a lot of self-confidence when it comes to Mathematics.				
12.	I understand quickly when solving with my class mate.				
13	I believe in multiple solutions to Mathematics problem.				
14.	I manipulate Mathematics objects.				
15.	Solving Mathematics is fun for me.				
16	I typically create new ideas from existing ones				
17	I deliberately ignore conventional ideas to come up with new ideas				
18	I do a lot of check and recheck work to come up with a new workable idea				
19	I identity everyday life problems and create mathematical solutions to it				
20	I often use the technique of brainstorming to create new ideas				